

Promoting Basic Educational Development in Nigeria through Teachers' Co-Creation of Learning

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Abstract

Basic education serves as the foundation for national development, social progress and lifelong learning. In Nigeria, improving the quality of basic education remains a priority due to persistent challenges such as inadequate learning outcomes, limited instructional innovation, and disparities in educational access and quality. This paper examined the role of teachers' co-creation of learning as a transformative approach to promoting basic educational development in Nigeria. Co-creation of learning involves collaborative processes in which teachers actively engage with colleagues, learners, school leaders, and other stakeholders to design, implement, and evaluate learning experiences that are responsive to learners' needs and contextual realities. The paper explored how collaborative learning design enhances teacher effectiveness, encourages professional knowledge sharing, and fosters innovative pedagogical practices. Through the participation in co-creation activities, teachers are better equipped to develop learner-centered strategies that improve student engagement, critical thinking, creativity, and academic achievement. The paper also highlighted the importance of supportive institutional structures, professional learning communities, and technology-enabled platforms that facilitate collaboration among educators. Drawing on relevant literature and contemporary educational practices, the study identifies key opportunities and challenges associated with implementing co-creation approaches in Nigerian basic education. The findings suggested that strengthening teachers' capacity for collaborative learning development can significantly improve instructional quality and educational outcomes. The paper concluded that teachers' co-creation of learning is a valuable strategy for fostering sustainable improvement and innovation in Nigeria's basic education system.

Keywords: Teachers' Co-Creation, Learning, Catalyst, Basic Education, Improvement, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

The quality of basic education depends largely on teachers' ability to create meaningful and engaging learning experiences. In Nigeria, collaborative learning design among educators offers a promising approach to educational improvement. Through co-creation of learning, teachers can share expertise, substitute innovation and enhance student achievement and overall educational development (Ololube, 2017).

Educational system across the developing country including Nigeria is battling with declining learning outcome, poor involvement of students, out-dated instructional material, non-adherence of standard, poor school plant, ineffectiveness of teachers due to resistance to change and innovation. Notwithstanding numerous educational reforms like curriculum upgrading, professional training, policy formulation, school free feeding programme in some primaries schools, better education service delivery for all (BESDA), hope education intervention and new pedagogical approach, sustainable improvement in Nigeria education has not yet achieved a sustainable educational system and this has in numerous ways affected the performances of students.

Basic education is the foundational stage of formal, non-formal and informal learning designed to meet essential needs, knowledge and skills needed for everyday life. The goals of basic education as state by the National Policy on Education:

- Provide the child with diverse basic knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship, wealth generation and educational advancement.
- Develop patriotic young people equipped to contribute to social development and in the performance of their civic responsibility
- Inculcate value and raise morally upright individual capable of independent thinking, and who appreciate the dignity of labour.
- Inspire national consciousness and harmonious co-existence, irrespective of differences in endowment, religion, colour, ethnic and social-economic background.
- Provide opportunities for the child to develop manipulative skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society within the limits of the child's capability.

To achieve a sustainable educational system, teachers who are the driving force of the educational system should be involved in moving beyond traditional top-down instruction to partnership driven approach. Co-creation of learning is aimed at providing partnership with the sole purpose of improving pedagogical skills and knowledge, enhance classroom management, increase job satisfaction and retention, improve student performance, and adoption of new technology. This professional development refers to continuous learning activities that helps teachers to improve their instructional practices, subject knowledge, classroom management and leadership skills in their daily teaching activities. It is not a one-time exercise, but a sustained reflective and collaborative process of growth. The aim of this in our educational system is to improve teachers' effectiveness, enhance student learning outcomes, update subject content knowledge, integrate technology effectively, develop leadership skills, mentoring skills and support curriculum changes.

The essence of teachers' co-creation in our schools is aimed at Improving classroom instruction, increase job satisfaction, better student achievement, higher teacher confidence, competence and stronger school culture. Teacher mentorship and teacher co-creation of learning

are deeply interconnected as effective professional development to equip teachers with innovative mindset, skills and structure needed to collaboratively aid teachers' co-creation of learning for improvement of our educational system. Continuous teacher professional development is highly relevant both for improving educational performance and effectiveness, and for enhancing teachers' commitment. A further aspect of professional development of teachers is the need for teachers to have the knowledge and skills to understand and implement the curriculum, related learning material and assessments. Teacher professional development provides the competencies that allow teachers to implement co-creative learning environment effectively.

The independent variable teacher co-creation simply means the practice of collaborating/ learning with others stakeholders (teachers/ students) to achieve a desirable aim. Co-creation means a collaborative pedagogical approach where different teachers or same subject teachers either from same school, different schools or LGA work together as partners in helping each other understand the act of effective teaching. Here, teachers work together to create components of curricula and pedagogical approach. In line with this study, co-creation has been described by Ryan and Tilbury (2013) as a new pedagogical idea that emphasises teachers' empowerment.

Teacher professional development enables co-creative learning by shifting teachers' mindsets, developing facilitation skills, building collaborative school culture, supporting curriculum flexibility and mutual reinforcement. Teacher professional development is the foundation that makes teachers' Co-creation of learning possible. Kasnakoglu and Mercan (2022) and Nguyen et al. (2021) opined that Co-creation has emerged as tentatively a pathway for understanding and studying the collaboration between educators and students.

CONCEPTUALIZATION

Types of Co-Creation of Learning

As earlier stated, Co-creation simply means the practice of learners collaborating with others. Co-creating of learning can be achieved through the following methods:

- **Mandatory Professional Development Meeting (MPDM):** This is a meeting of teachers in a school which is meant primarily to encourage peer support among teachers as well as enable them share experiences on how best to improve teaching and learning in the classroom, it can also be said that another purpose of MPD meeting in schools is to discuss challenges observed during lesson observation by the head, and proffer solutions, sharing among teachers the good practices that would lead to effective teaching and learning in classrooms. Members of Mpdm includes the head teacher or principal depending on the level of education, their assistants and teachers.
- **School Based Training:** is a professional development model where groups of teachers come together to interact acquire knowledge and skills needed to improve their pedagogical approach to teaching.

Aim of School Base Teachers' Co-Creation

- Provide assistance to the school teachers in implementing the skills and knowledge acquired

- Obtain adequate information on school- based teachers
 - Develop the monitoring skills of education managers.
- Lesson study: This is a form of inquiry by group of teachers on lesson taught in classrooms in order to determine ways of improving the learning outcome. It is a form or research aimed at finding out learners /teachers’ problem, or needs in any particular topic or subject. Lesson study enables teachers to acquire skills on how to design suitable teaching methods; it aids teachers to identify teaching problems among themselves. For effective collaboration in planning lesson study teachers adopt the following steps:

Benefits of lesson study teachers co-creation:

- It encourages teachers to work together and carry out research on how to seek better ways of teaching
 - Lesson study provides opportunity for teachers to learn from each other and grow professionally
 - It improves classroom practices as teachers have used each other as students in enhancing their teaching practice
 - It enhances co creation among teachers in the school.
- School support officers (SSO’S): These are personnel who provide professional support to classroom teachers these officers include education managers and education secretaries. Their support is based on knowledge and skills acquired in the course of the teacher professional development training and other innovation introduced in the teaching

and learning process. The school support officers conduct cluster teachers meeting where they collaborate and proffer solution to problems encountered by the teachers.

- Teacher/Student co-creation: This method involves partnership between teachers and students in forming their own learning experiences. Here students are active participants rather than passive participants. (Harden & Lilley, 2018) opined that one of the future roles of a teacher in education is to engage learners in education program and consider equal partners rather than consumers of education.

EXAMPLES OF TEACHER'S/STUDENT'S CO-CREATION OF LEARNING

- Pedagogical co-design: Both parties work hand in hand to create learning activities
- Co-research- Learner and educator research together, to investigate, analyze and enhance teaching and learning practices.
- Consultation/Partnership classroom: Students give feedbacks and contribute on course policies.
- Curriculum Negotiation: Educators and learners work in synergy to decide learning objectives, content and assignment rather than adhering to a fixed syllabus. In support with the above view Voogt et al. (2026) affirmed that teachers are called upon to collaborate in designing new curriculum or tailoring of new practices with well-known benefits of professional development.

BENEFITS OF TEACHERS' CO-CREATION OF LEARNING

Some of the most visible benefits of co-creation of learning are:

- Promoting /encouraging of critical thinking- when teachers work together to create new ideas, solve problem, they commit to thoughtful interaction and reasoning. This in turn helps to enhance their ability to interpret information, critically reason and make sound and reasonable conclusion.
- It encourages effective interaction and partnership among teachers, when teachers co - create they share ideals clearly, listen actively, provide productive /beneficial feedback and build common grounds or collection of opinion.
- Teachers co-creation of learning creates opportunity for social interaction, teachers get to know their colleagues better, understand various position and build relationship. This social aspect plays a vital role in teachers' engagement and motivation. It creates better relationship, encourages trust and deeper interrelation among all groups.
- Teachers' co-creation of learning enhances quality, teachers produce meaningful, context-specific and effective learning material
- Teachers' co-creation of learning creates independence; this independence increases students and teachers' motivation through shared ownership and voice.

CHALLENGES OF TEACHER CO-CREATION

- Teachers do not set rules and regulation that guides the effective implementation of co-creation meeting. Roles and responsibilities are not well defined leading to confusion about who is responsible for what and vague goals. (Mathews et al., 2018)
- Different opinion comes to play resulting to ineffective implementation of co-creation of learning (Eric, 2017).
- Teachers' inability to spend quality time with colleagues regularly would create a hindrance in working effectively with their colleagues in the course of co-creation with each other.
- This can lead to inefficiency and decreased productivity, too many teachers trying to teach together or at once, or having an over bearing influence can be a distraction when implementing teachers' co-creation of learning.
- This occurs when teachers still want to maintain their traditional methods of teaching rather than embrace the innovative pedagogy of teaching.
- This occurs when teacher fails to recognize her strength, this denotes one's ability to think, relate and define feelings (Flavin, 2016).

This paper argued that teachers' co-creation of learning serves as a strong catalyst for educational improvement in Nigeria. For clarity sake teachers' co-creation of learning is a collaborative strategy among teachers to proffer solutions to educational challenges. The process emphasises that groups of educators jointly design lesson plans, topic analysis, lesson context, instructional strategies, relevant teaching/learning materials and agree on a given time for discussion, practicum and necessary professional improvement.

Also Cook-sather et al. in Catherine (2020) defines co-creation as a collaborative reciprocal process through which all participants have the opportunity to contribute equally, although not necessarily in the same ways to curriculum or pedagogical conceptualization, decision making, implementation, investigation or analysis. Also Ryan and T.bury (2013) affirms that co-creation is a new pedagogical idea that emphasises learner empowerment. In support of the above definition Bovil and Worlmer (2018) opined that co-creation in learning and teaching involves inviting a group of teachers or learners who come together in any teaching setting, be it face to face, or online, to activity collaborate and negotiate with each other on how to improve teaching and learning.

The negotiation might be the content or subject matter, the purpose of their work, the teaching approach, the manner in which they can improve teaching and learning outcome together or in their preferred design to education. In co-creation the purpose, approaches, contents and outcomes of learning and teaching are collaboratively agreed that there is a shared responsibility for colleagues to carryout. Co-creation involves developing deeper relationships between professional colleagues. Education is perceived as shared responsibility for colleagues who are interested in solving educational challenges.

In order to improve the educational system, teachers' co-creation targets to address the following perceived challenges in teaching:

- Isolation of teachers
- Over-reliance on traditional pedagogy
- Inconsistent curriculum implementation

- Limited professional development

Teachers' isolation

According to Adebayo and Amos (2025), teachers' isolation refers to the physical and psychological separation of educators from their professional colleagues, it is often displayed by having limited opportunities to share collaborate or discuss techniques leading to increased burnout and reduced professional development. It is often seen in the egg-crate school structure where teachers are confined to their own classroom.

Types of Teachers' Isolation

- Physical/structural isolation: it is often described as the "egg-crate" model, where teachers are separated into individual, closed door classroom with little time or opportunity to interact with professional colleagues during the day. This hinders the flow of information or communication between colleagues. Agwu (2022) described teacher isolation as one of the main structural impediments to improve instruction and student learning in American public schools. In support of the above view, Cargerin (2019) opined that collaboration among teachers is an essential aspect of instructional improvement.
- Psychological isolation: This is a situation where a teacher feels emotionally or mentally disconnected from others, due to loneliness or psychological issues. The teacher feels unguided, unsupported, unmentored, misunderstood or personally responsible for all pedagogical decision (Ahmad, 2025).

Causes of Psychological Isolation

- Classroom Structure: Teacher spend most of their time alone with students.
- Lack of collegial support: Limited partnership time or unsupportive school cultures reduces meaningful peer connection
- Administrative pressure: High expectations, evaluations, and policy changes can create stress without emotional backing.
- Emotional labor: Teacher constantly regulate their emotions while supporting students, often suppressing their own stress.
- Role Ambiguity: Balancing educator, counsellor, disciplinarians and communication role can feel overwhelming.
- Studies in educational psychology has linked teacher isolation to reduced school climate quality and lower collaboration levels.
- Environmental /Geographical Isolation: This is common in the rural, remote areas or small schools where a teacher may be the only specialist in their subject, it refers also to the challenges learners and school face due to physical remoteness or difficult environmental condition that limit access to educational resources, personnel, and opportunities. This kind of isolation affects job satisfaction and ability to perform at their best.

To address teachers' isolation school culture should be changed in order to encourage scheduled collaborative time, interaction and support systems.

Over-Reliance on Traditional Pedagogy

The purpose of education is to address the contemporary issues in the society. Over-reliance on traditional pedagogy makes Nigeria educational system unproductive because of its obsolete approach in handling challenges and meeting up global expectation in this artificial intelligent era. Over-reliance makes approach heavily dependent on lectures, rote memorization and standardized testing which often leads to disengagement and stifled creativity. This over-reliance on traditional pedagogy is characterized with passive learning, lack of personalization, limited creativity, inefficiency and rigidity.

Inconsistent Curriculum Implementation

Curriculum implementation refers to how teachers deliver instruction and assessment through the use of specified resources provided in the curriculum. Inconsistent curriculum implementation occurs when the planned official curriculum is delivered unequally across classrooms, schools, or regions, leading to disparities in students learning. The inconsistent curriculum implementation is seen in teacher driven discrepancies lack of vertical alignment, resource and infrastructure gap, uneven administrative focus and frequent system changes.

Consequences of Inconsistent Implementation

- Learning Gaps: Learners in different classes receive different levels of education hindering fair academic progress.
- Lowered performance and Lack of standardized: High-quality instruction leads to poor student outcomes and confusion.
- Waste of Resources: Developing new curricula becomes a waste of time if they are not implemented uniformly.

Limited Professional Development

Professional development refers to improving oneself through learning and training to advance career. School management may offer training sessions to upgrade their teaching skills and knowledge, but in the teachers', co-creation learning teachers typically advance on their own professional development independently.

So limited professional development means restricted, infrequent or narrowly focused opportunities for employees to enhance their skills, knowledge and career growth, it is often caused by scarce resources, lack of support from employer and significant time constraints, which hinder long-time career advancement and skill.

Features Leading to Limited Professional Development

- Scarce opportunities: Few or no workshop training sessions, conferences or certification programs provided by the employer.

- Time and resource constraints: High workloads, lack of budget or lack of support leadership
- Narrow focus: Training is restricted to immediate, short-term job tasks rather than comprehensive, long term skill acquisition.

In view to harness limited professional development, teachers' co-creation of learning is the fastest and rational way to impact educational system without much logistic and financial input.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To further elucidates how teachers' co-creation of learning serves as a catalyst for educational improvement in Nigeria, the paper is anchored on constructive theory propounded by Piaget as cited in Daodu et al. (2024). The theory states that learning occurs when participants are actively involved in a process of knowledge and meaningful construction as opposed to passively receiving information. Constructivist teaching fosters thinking, creates motivated and independent learners. The theory posits that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction with their environment rather than passively receiving information. Learning therefore is experiment, social and reflective. Teachers co creation of learning aligns strongly with constructivism because both emphasizes on:

- Active learner participation;
- Social interaction in knowledge construction;
- Shared responsibility in knowledge process.

The relevance of this constructivism theory argues that participants (teachers or learners) learn best when they are actively involved in building knowledge. Teacher co-creation is achieved through engagement of teachers in lesson planning discussion, allowing colleagues to contribute ideas, perspectives and encouraging inquiry- based learning (IBL) tasks, instead of being knowledge transmitters teachers become facilitators of learning. Co-creation of learning is rooted in the power of collective knowledge and group interaction, notwithstanding its contextual flexibility, certain inherent attributes pervade all forms of co-creation of learning. Knowing these key features can be a utensil in implementing this educational strategy and reaping its benefits.

In support of the above view, Catherine (2019) affirmed that co-creation of learning entails cooperative efforts and the exchange of information among group members. Co-creation operates on the ground of mutual interdependence which believes that individual success depends on group success. In view of the above, Lina et al. (2020) state that teachers' co-creation of learning involves a group of two or more learners working dependently with each other to achieve a common goal respecting each individual's contribution to the whole.

Another main aspect of Co-creation of learning is that it encourages positive interaction between participants, these findings are in view with Remay-Lyn (2023), who opined that co-creation of learning engages student-student, student-teacher and student-content interactions. These attributes distinguish teachers' co-creation of learning from other work, it argued that participants should actively engage one another in transforming their understanding through communication and exchange of feedback and share in decision making. To support the above view, Tupele-Ebi and Benneth (2025) attest that teachers co-creation of learning is considered as a process involving a sequence of actions undertaken by teachers and students, teachers and

teachers grounded in a reciprocal relationship. Teachers' co-creation of learning allows for open dialogue and communication of ideas between teachers and students, teachers and teachers. Teachers' co-creation of learning is not merely a style but rather an answer to the changing needs call-for in our learning environment, society and nation at large.

However, this digital age places implicit values on collaboration, critical thinking, creativity and communication skills which teachers' co-creation of learning seeks to develop. Teachers' co-creation of learning encourages the use of other skills, which includes the 3 domain specific skills (psycho-motor, cognitive and affective). In support of the above, research has proposed that teachers' co-creation of learning enhances cognitive, social and emotional learning outcomes. It encourages students to engage in higher-order thinking and enables them to develop skills such as negotiation, problem-solving and critical reflection (Nhuyen, 2023)

In nutshell, constructive theory provided philosophical and pedagogical backbone for teacher co-creation of learning. It validates the view that learning is most effective when participants (teachers) actively participate in planning, shaping and building their educational experiences. Another notable theory in this paper is cooperative theory by John Dewey in the early 20th century cited in Adabayo and Amos (2025), the theory posits that education is a social process based on experience, collaboration and active participation. He asserted that learning in small groups, different ability groups foster's democratic skills, communication and critical thinking.

Teacher co-creation of learning shares similitude of key variables in cooperative learning theory, such as learning through experience (experiential learning) socialization and democracy, active interaction.

Co-creation of learning is in consonant with engagement according to Onyia et al. (2024), the assumption is that participants (learners) must be meaningfully engaged through collaborative and project-based tasks. It focuses on the "Relate-create Donate model" which prompts team interaction and creative problem solving and real- world application to boost motivation and knowledge retention.

The above theory is relevant in this teacher co-creation of learning because it asserted that learning occurs through collaborative teams, communication and social interaction. Note the key elements (collaborative teams) communication and social interaction aims at problem solving which is core target of co-creation.

ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN TEACHERS' COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

Stakeholders are characters/personage or cluster of persons that has a vested interest in the success and welfare of an organization. Stakeholders in any organization are important because their collective effort raises the chances in reaching the organizational goals. In education Stakeholders play a crucial role in enhancing the teaching /learning process, supporting this view is (Chang & Huang, 2022) who opined Stakeholder participation can enhance the theoretical understanding and practical skills of students and teachers. These stakeholders are teachers, parents, students, community and government.

THE ROLES OF TEACHERS IN CO-CREATION OF TRAINING IN THE SCHOOL

During co-creation training of teachers, teachers shift from delivering pre-set curricular to becoming facilitators and partners, collaborating with students to design learning outlines, goals, activities and possible assessment. The role of teachers' co-creation is as follows:

- Promotes teacher active engagement;
- Building trust;
- Enhancing student learning outcome;
- Supporting school improvement and reform;
- Dissemination or cascading skills acquired through teacher development and growth.

Promoting teacher active engagement- Co-creation promotes teacher active engagement by assigning responsibilities to individual teachers with a specific task to handle during the meeting or discussion period. When teachers consistently implement co-creation training, they can assist their colleagues develop new skills, refine instructional practices and improve the overall educational system (Maria & Theodosios, 2023).

Building Trust through Co-creation: Co-creation builds trust by changing the traditional practices, hierarchical teacher head-teacher relationship into a partnership based on shared responsibility, mutual respect and reciprocal learning. Group of teachers coming together in decision-making such as in curriculum design or assessment methods. This working together on educational goals brings mutual accountability and trust among teachers. In the case of teacher-students co-creation, it increases trust in the teachers' commitment to their success. It also disrupts traditional authority structure, shifting the role of the principal or school head from expert to a partner in learning which encourages openness. This collaborative nature of co-creation enhances transparency and strengthens personal connection.

Enhancing student learning outcome: Co-creation of learning improves learning outcome by shifting learners from passive recipients to active collaborators. In the educational process it encourages deeper engagement, participation and ownership.

Supporting School improvement and reform: Co-creation is essential for supporting educational improvement and reform initiatives, when teachers effectively implement partnership, it helps to harness educational imbalances or educational gaps among teachers which in turn improves educational system.

Disseminating or cascading skills: Co-creation is a very vital means of spreading skills and knowledge acquired by few persons during professional development programme. It helps disseminate information by breaking down shared pedagogical practices, resources and insights.

Technology and Teachers' Co-Creation of Learning

Technology plays a pivotal role in facilitating teachers' co-creation of learning by enabling the sharing of instructional materials, collaborative lesson planning, and professional interaction through digital platforms. Through technological tools, educators can transcend geographical barriers and collaborate effectively on pedagogical strategies and instructional innovations. One of the most significant contributions of technology to co-creation is its support for virtual communication. Digital platforms such as Skype, Google Meet, and Zoom enable real-time

interaction and collaboration among teachers, students, and other educational stakeholders regardless of location (CER Education, 2025).

Furthermore, technology promotes collaborative learning environments by enabling the establishment of virtual classrooms where instructional materials can be accessed and shared. Within these environments, teachers and students engage in discussions, brainstorming sessions, group projects, and feedback activities. Cloud-based applications such as Google Workspace facilitate knowledge sharing by allowing multiple users to create, edit, review, and store documents simultaneously. These collaborative technologies also enhance participants' digital competencies and technical skills. According to Norgko et al. (2024), technology ensures equitable participation and access to collaborative learning processes for both teachers and students.

Technology also supports co-creation through educational games and simulation programs. These tools combine learning with engagement and create opportunities for teachers and learners to work collaboratively toward common objectives while developing teamwork, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

Additionally, technology facilitates data-driven decision-making by enabling teachers to collect, analyze, and interpret student performance data collaboratively. Such information assists educators in adjusting instructional strategies and designing personalized learning experiences. Supporting this perspective, Zamista and Azmi (2023) observed that digital technologies enable teachers to monitor student progress effectively without disrupting collaborative learning activities.

Innovative technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) further enhance co-creation by providing immersive and interactive learning experiences. These technologies enable educators to design engaging instructional environments that foster active participation and collaborative knowledge construction. Zikri (2024) emphasized that digital competence among teachers is essential for maximizing the educational benefits of technology in collaborative learning environments.

Roles of Parents in the Co-Creation of Training in Schools

Parents are among the most influential stakeholders in education because their involvement significantly contributes to students' academic achievement and overall development. Research by Abdulrahman and Madugu (2014) demonstrated that parental involvement and interest significantly influence students' achievement in Mathematics in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Parents contribute to the co-creation of educational experiences through various activities. They collaborate with teachers by attending parent-teacher meetings, participating in open days, reviewing their children's academic work, and discussing academic progress with educators (Newman et al., 2019). Such interactions strengthen the partnership between home and school and facilitate the development of strategies that support student learning.

In addition, parents support learning at home by creating conducive learning environments, demonstrating interest in their children's academic activities, establishing regular study routines, and assisting with homework. Ramirez et al. (2022) emphasized that effective parental involvement includes providing families with information and resources that enable them to support children's learning at home.

Parents also participate in educational governance through School Boards and Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs). Their involvement in decision-making processes contributes to

improved educational outcomes. According to Sakaue, Wokadala, and Ogawa (2023), sustained parental participation in advocacy, decision-making, fundraising, volunteering, and home-based teaching positively influences student achievement. In Nigeria, Parent-Teacher Associations play a crucial role in promoting parental engagement in educational policy and school development.

Furthermore, parents make decisions regarding their children's participation in extracurricular activities and help cultivate positive attitudes toward education. Such attitudes enhance students' motivation, engagement, and commitment to learning.

Importance of Parents as Stakeholders

Parents contribute significantly to educational success through the following roles:

- Promoting high academic achievement among students.
- Strengthening communication between the home and school. Haisraeli and Fogiel-Bijaoui (2023) argued that effective two-way communication between schools and families is essential for student success.
- Improving student attendance and behavioral regulation.
- Supporting students' emotional and social development through guidance and mentorship.
- Assisting in identifying and utilizing community resources that enhance students' learning and development (Epstein, 2018).

Parents are therefore critical stakeholders because they share responsibility with schools for students' educational success and collaborate with teachers to create supportive learning environments.

CONCLUSION

The paper strongly posits that teacher co-creation of learning is a transformative approach or strategy for improving Nigeria educational system. It helps to strengthen instructional quality, promote innovation and ensure long-term systemic reform. The study emphatically stated that isolated teaching strategy cannot improve the educational system; this is because the strength of every system depends on effective teamwork. Therefore, co-creation among teachers, students, parents, community, and government improve teaching effectiveness, enhance problem-solving, promote innovation and ensure better learning outcomes.

Suggestions

- Teacher's co-creation of learning should be made compulsory to close educational gaps or indifference that exist.
- Teacher's co-creation should be implemented to develop open communication, empathy, and mutual respect to support collaborative relationship or partnership.
- Adoption of co-creation of learning would revitalize and re-build Nigeria's educational system.
- Collaboration or co-creation remains a rational approach to provide the structure and philosophical foundation for improving basic educational system in Nigeria.

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